
Analysis of Key Financial Indicators that Influence the Stability Rating of Commercial Banks

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Abstract: This article analyses the impact of financial indicators, including liquidity, capital adequacy, profitability, asset quality and risk management, on rating indicators. Statistical and economic modelling methods are used as a methodological approach, and practical analysis is carried out using the example of commercial banks in Uzbekistan. The results of the study can be used in the development of strategic recommendations for improving the efficiency of banking activities, increasing investment attractiveness, and improving sustainability ratings.

Key words: Rating of commercial banks, investments, liquidity, capital, national rating system, financial institutions.

INTRODUCTION

In today's global economic environment, the financial stability of commercial banks is one of the main pillars of the country's economy. The stability of the banking system directly affects not only the effective organisation of banks' activities but also the overall development of the national economy. Therefore, in assessing the performance of banks, their financial indicators, in particular, the level of liquidity, capital adequacy, profitability indicators and asset quality, play an important role.

This study aims to study the main financial indicators that affect the stability rating of commercial banks, thereby analysing the possibilities of increasing the efficiency and competitiveness of banking activities. The study uses statistical and economic modelling methods and conducts a practical analysis of the example of commercial banks in Uzbekistan. The results of this study can be used in making strategic decisions to strengthen the stability of banks.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article uses statistical and economic modelling methods based on the results of econometric modelling and conducts a practical analysis of the example of commercial banks in Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

News about the positive rating of commercial banks or the entire banking system arouses interest among the population and local entrepreneurs. Because such information cannot but affect their decision-making in their daily financial activities. In particular, it affects the decisions of bank shareholders and investors, as well as the government and other financial institutions. The rating is a complex indicator of the world's leading rating agencies, which characterises the financial and economic condition of the bank and differs from the simplest ratios, such as the capital adequacy ratio. Therefore, interest in determining the procedure for determining the rating of commercial banks is very high. This method should allow for comparing the condition of a specific bank among commercial banks. Moody's and Standard and Poor's rating agencies own 40% of the global rating services market. The Fitch Ratings rating agency (14% of the debt bond market) completes the top three. The ratings of these three rating agencies are considered expert since their

rules and the information they receive are considered closed information. Despite the fact that rating agencies publish a narrow description of the factors taken into account when forming ratings, banks can find out exactly which factors affect the rating indicators developed by the agencies and which changes in them can make the bank's rating attractive.

Taking into account the above, we can determine that the purpose of the study is to examine the correlations between the economic and financial indicators of commercial banks and the published rating indicators. The results may indicate that it is possible to influence the bank rating using the focused elements of financial policy. The rating indicators determined by rating agencies are of great importance for the country's financial stability. The rating indicator plays a major role in attracting credit lines from international financial institutions to commercial banks of Uzbekistan. Following the international financial crisis, investor confidence in rating indicators has eroded due to financial losses, and therefore, many countries, including Uzbekistan, have considered measures to regulate rating agencies domestically.

For example, within the framework of the instructions of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Association of Banks of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Finance, a system of development of a national rating system and its constant monitoring has been introduced. In addition, it should be noted that the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan has formed a reduced list of rating agencies that assess the ratings of commercial banks of Uzbekistan. Interest in research related to rating agencies arose after the adoption by the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision of the document "On Capital Assessment and International Consensus of Capital Standards" (Basel 2, 2004). This document contains methodological recommendations on the regulation of the activities of commercial banks, in particular, requirements and proposals for organisations performing financial regulatory functions in assessing the credit risk of borrowers at all levels when accounting for bank assets and taking into account their ratings assessed by international rating agencies. However, some economists (Kanata and Quaylarello, 2010) criticise the Basel II requirements in their scientific works. The methodologies and theories related to developing ratings and rating systems are diverse. They are divided into two directions:

- 1) the opinions put forward by commercial banks themselves on determining ratings;
- 2) the opinions of external participants (government, investors and customers).

The goal of the first research direction is to reveal the essence of ratings and critically analyze them. The second direction aims to test hypotheses about the characteristics and application of ratings. Economists Howe et al., in their article, tried to forecast the indicators of the three largest rating agencies in the world and compare the quality of their rating systems. The authors confirmed in their research that the quality of ratings depends on the state of the financial system, and during the financial crisis, various rating systems served as a very important source of information [1]. In their opinion, it is impossible to predict the expected "risk" based on ratings, given the investment rating of a bank. When calculating ratings, major rating agencies must take into account the diversity of requirements for financial reporting in countries. The policies of the agencies regarding various factors also differ from each other. For example, Standard and Poor's assesses the impact of bank size and country factors more strictly than Moody's and Fitch ratings. In most cases, a bank's rating depends on the relationship between the agency and the bank, as well as the rating value, size and activities of the banks. According to the authors, various forms of state support for banks (neutral participation, government guarantees) do not affect the rating of banks.

- After the crisis, many studies focused on the effectiveness of commercial banks in terms of bank risks and profitability. For example, it was found that commercial banks with a first-rate capital adequacy ratio and a high loan-to-asset ratio performed well in the early stages of the crisis. Economists Berger and Bowman showed in their scientific work that during the crisis, a high level of capital led to an increase in the efficiency of banks, and deposits and highly liquid assets brought them more income[2].

- In addition, the transparency and openness of information related to the activities of banks also had a significant impact. The flow of information available through the Internet networks has determined the impact on bank ratings (but only ratings by independent rating agencies). It is said that commercial banks that do not apply to rating agencies for a rating but continue to widely disclose information about their activities can achieve great success in obtaining a high rating level. Pagano et al. studied the forecasting of rating changes based on financial reporting data. The authors make the following points[3]:
- It is easier to predict an increase in a rating than a decrease;
- Bank financial reporting indicators are of great importance in predicting changes, but their importance varies for large and small banks;
- Financial reporting indicators can more accurately predict the prospects for changes in the rating indicators of banks engaged in traditional lending operations than for financial institutions operating in financial markets. The competitive environment between rating agencies can also impact the quality of ratings. This issue was also studied in the scientific work of Bolton et al.[4]. As we noted above, a bank rating is determined by empirical calculations that summarise financial and qualitative indicators. This model is based on the AHP method, which comprehensively evaluates quantitative data, indicating internal and external factors. In the process of forming an econometric model, we initially compiled a list of 17 Uzbek commercial banks. These 17 selected banks all have the information we need and have received an international rating. It should be noted that all commercial banks in Uzbekistan have an international rating indicator. The financial statements of these 17 commercial banks for 2021-2024, as well as ratings issued by 3 international rating agencies, are included. Due to our obligation not to disclose bank data, the content of the bank rating and data is not presented in numbers. The justification for using scaling with numbers is that a small number of banks are being analyzed. The numerical value of the given rating indicator represents the independent variable. The financial indicators of the bank's account provided by the information and rating agency are considered as explanatory variables. All variables have a quantitative value.

In the modeling process, we use the following variables:

act_vol – characterizes the volume of bank assets;

own_cap – characterizes private equity;

cred-portf – characterizes the placement of loans;

cred_vol – characterizes the volume of loans with a term extension;

inv_portf – characterizes the volume of investments (portfolio);

firm_dep – characterizes deposits of legal entities in the bank;

ind_dep – characterizes deposits of individuals in the bank;

net_profit – characterizes the total annual net profit;

act_profit – characterizes the profitability of bank assets;

owncap_profit – characterizes the profitability of private equity.

The limited number of independent variables is explained by the impossibility of finding other types of data on the activities of banks when determining the data. The logarithmic form of the variables in the model is manipulated by converting the amount of variables into percentage units. The model did not include some independent variables due to uncertain values during the Dickey-Fuller tool and correlation analysis.

The table below shows the results of the econometric modelling of bank ratings for 2021-2024. The table contains the confidence levels of independent variables with a confidence level of 5% to 10%.

Table-1
Results of econometric modeling of bank ratings for 2021-24

	Variables	Explanation ratio
1	cred_portf/own_cap	4.076%
2	log(firm_dep)	9.256%
3	log(ind_dep)	6.746%
4	log(inv_portf)	- 9.062%
5	log(net_porfit)	2.242%
6	owncap_profit	0.187%
7	act_profit	4.973%
8	others	63.459%

From Table 1, we can see that the explanatory power of all indicators is very low. This was expected from the analysis because we included in the model only those variables that, according to economic theory, are most suitable for explaining the dependent variables and the data available to us. The selected variables are calculated only based on financial statement data, no other internal or external factors are considered. However, rating agencies also take into account internal and external factors. The search for financial factors that affect the rating creates great opportunities for bank managers to improve their position. If they knew which factors are taken into account by rating agencies, they would have spent all their efforts on developing this very area. The accepted value of the R2 of the model (which indicates the closeness of the economic variables in this model) was taken as 0.71. The accepted ratio is also usually used to compare models with different ordered factors to ensure that these ordered factors do not affect the R2 statistic.

In our case, the established ratio is 0.64. The sum of squared residuals is taken as the smallest value in the regression. The standard error of the regression is taken as close to 0. The probability of the F-statistics being equal to 0 is the most important factor characterizing the reliability and accuracy of the regression. The OLS model is selected according to the following three criteria under the condition of the smallest value: the Akaike information criterion, the Schwarz criterion, the Hannan-Quinn criterion. The Durbin-Watson stat criterion turned out to be the ideal criterion. Regression analysis calculated by the OLS method was checked with Gauss-Markov and other existing analyses.

Based on the results of the analysis of data on commercial banks of Uzbekistan, we came to the following conclusions:

- We believe that the selected variables determine the quality of the rating indicators assigned to the state of banks, and the factors taken into account in the model explain the bank rating by an average of 63.5%;
- In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the more deposits of legal entities and individuals in a bank, the higher the credit rating of this bank;
- it should be taken into account that enterprises and other valuable securities on the balance sheet of commercial banks of Uzbekistan do not always bring profit to the bank. The higher the bank's investment portfolio, the lower the rating indicator;
- the higher the ratio of the commercial bank's loan portfolio to its equity (impact level \approx 4.076%), the higher the bank's rating;
- also, an increase in the bank's annual net profit for the year under analysis by up to 2% affects the bank's rating for the following year;

- the rating is not affected at all by the amount of private capital available to the bank in the total cash flow;
- the quality of assets and their profitability are considered one of the most influential factors in justifying the rating.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- Based on the results of the study, it is possible to draw conclusions and put forward many recommendations for commercial banks in Uzbekistan:
- Banks should continue to actively attract idle funds of the population and, mainly, legal entities serving these banks;
- the larger the volume of short-term current assets, the more profit will be received and the higher the rating will be;
- banks are not recommended to invest heavily in corporate securities and engage in investment activities in the stock market; instead, it is better to engage in traditional banking activities.

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